

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE PEDAGOGICAL REFORMS CARRIED OUT IN THE IMPROVEMENT OF THE PIRLS INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT PROGRAM

Avazova Durдона Erkinovna

Teacher of the Department “Mother tongue in primary education and methods of teaching it”,
Faculty of primary education of TSPU named after Nizami

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7707427>

Abstract. *This article compares the level and quality of text comprehension by elementary school students in the international PIRLS study. The reforms carried out in the republic and methodological recommendations and pedagogical technologies aimed at identifying students' reading literacy are also presented.*

Keywords: *PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS, IEA, Construct, artistic experience, pedagogical innovations, technologies, information technologies, international study of reading, competencies, concepts of reading and literacy.*

Decree No. 5712 of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29. 2019 “on approval of the concept of development of the system of public education of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” in the ranking of the PIRLS International Assessment Program by 2030, the tasks of creating a national system for assessing the quality of education aimed at assessing the level of.

Also, on December 8. 2018. the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on measures to organize international research in the field of assessing the quality of education in the system of public education, to establish international relations, to comprehensively support and encourage the research and innovative activities of students and young people, and, above all, creative ideas and creativity. According to the decision, the goal of raising the growing younger generation to a qualitatively new level of spiritual, moral and intellectual development, the introduction of innovative forms and methods of education into the educational process necessitates a mechanism for further improvement of the national system of development of the intellectual potential of students and young people .

Since 1958, the international Association for the assessment of achievements in the field of Education (IEA) has been conducting comparative studies on the identification of knowledge, skills, qualifications and competencies of students in the field of Education. In particular, the Republic of Uzbekistan has established cooperation with the International Association for the assessment of the quality of Education (IEA) in order to improve the quality and effectiveness of education and to study foreign best practices.

Most of the research carried out by the IEA organization involves an assessment of the academic performance of students from one or more disciplines or on the basis of interdisciplinary coherence, which contributes to an in-depth analysis of educational processes in general and in the context of each country in the world . To this end, within the framework of the "development strategy for seven priority areas of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" approved by the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 27, 2022 No. 60" on the development

strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", a system was formed based on the determination and comparison of the new monitoring system.

Decree No. 5712 of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 "on approval of the concept of development of the system of public education of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" in the ranking of the international program PIRLS by 2030, the tasks of creating a national system for assessing the quality of education aimed at assessing the level of. Within the framework of the concept, taking into account the special emphasis on the development of critical thinking, independent search for information, analysis skills and competencies of students, the introduction of comprehensive programs and new state educational standards that meet the requirements of the modern innovative economy, constant participation in international PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS and other programs for assessing the quality of Education. On the way to the implementation of these tasks, a special place is occupied by successful participation in PIRLS research.

The PIRLS program was founded in 2001 by the International Association for the assessment of educational achievements (IEA–International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement), a program focused on comparing the work and results carried out in the national education system of different countries of the world on reading literacy.

The PIRLS 2021 international study examines the needs for a wide range of complex questions and the adaptation of these questions to the abilities of students by introducing a unified assessment procedure based on a number of new assessment criteria. The new assessment procedure is based on texts of three different levels of complexity – complex, average and easy – formed as a result of combining an assessment Book of two different levels of complexity. A more complex grading notebook is made up of one medium complexity and one complex structured text, while an easier grading notebook is composed of one easy and one medium complexity or two easy texts. Each participating country conducts the entire assessment process themselves, but the balance between complex and easy assessment notebooks can vary depending on the degree of readability of students in the country. For example, a country with an average reading mastery rate (an average score of 550 or higher)

Reading literacy serves as the basis for the growth of students' scientific and personal success, and is also a valuable tool for assessing the impact of the policy pursued in the field of education on success.

The concepts of reading and Reading Literacy have changed over the years and are reflected in the fields of society, economics, culture and technology. Reading has ceased to be considered a skill that is mastered only in the early stages of education, in childhood.

This view of Reading Literacy reflects many reading theories as a constructive and interactive process. In the process of the reader's work with the text, through communication between the reader and the text (which is why this process is called Interactive), the reader creates a meaning (that is why this process is called constructive English "construct" – create). The reader is an active participant in this process, creates meaning, observes Over the text and consciously selectively applies effective reading strategies. Each type of text helps the reader interpret the text, following the usual form and rules. Any text can have different shapes. These include traditional books, magazines, documents, and newspapers, as well as Digital-looking written forms. PIRLS focuses on two comprehensive goals of younger students' classroom and extracurricular learning. These are studies to gain artistic experience and to obtain and use information .

In short, the degree to which students master reading literacy continues to be one of the most important characteristics of the demand of today. This section reveals important aspects of the development of Reading Literacy, conscious reading skills in students in preparation for participation in international studies on the assessment of students' literacy. That is, if the concept of reading is simply considered the ability to read a text, then the concept of reading literacy requires a conscious, understanding reading of the text that the reader is reading in it, covering a wide range of reading skills. In reading literacy, the reader is required to understand written texts by reading them, be able to apply them in different situations and be able to apply them in social life.

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